

13.4 MHz FDML Laser for Intra-Surgical Optical Coherence Tomography

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Fourier domain mode locked (FDML) lasers are rapidly swept laser sources which are predominantly used for optical coherence tomography (OCT), a non-invasive depth resolving imaging modality [1]. State of the art FDML lasers achieve sweep repetition rates up to 5.2 MHz enabling MHz-OCT with video update rates and meter long coherence lengths allowing for working distances of several centimeters [2, 3]. Recently, researchers are pursuing the goal to implement MHz-OCT into surgical microscopes assisting the surgeon to get intra-operative guidance and identification of tumor infiltration [4]. During surgery, high resolution OCT-volumes ($>1024 \times 1024$ A-Scans) with video update rates (>24 fps) are required which is a speed beyond the standard MHz-OCT capabilities. These prerequisites demand A-Scan rates exceeding 10 MHz. To meet these requirements, we present an FDML laser with 13.4 MHz sweep repetition rate sweeping over 113 nm centered at 1300 nm.

The setup of the FDML laser is similar to the one described in [3] with a boosted optical amplifier (BOA, Thorlabs BOA1130S), a custom-designed chirped fiber Bragg grating (CFBG) to minimize dispersion, a custom-built fiber Fabry-Pérot tunable Filter (FFP-TF), an isolator and a circulator. The design of the FFP-TF has been updated to allow for wide sweep bandwidths at shorter BOA modulation duty cycles of 3.0 % compared to previous setups. Further a new FFP-TF driver was designed to achieve a stable operation in the ultra-stable regime (sweet spot). To optimize synchronization of all components different strategies were evaluated and implemented. The fundamental sweep repetition rate is $\sim 419,124$ Hz yielding to a sweep repetition rate of ~ 13.4 MHz after 32x optical buffering.

In Fig. 1 (a) the output spectrum of the FDML laser is shown. The bandwidth of the sweep is 113 nm. The wavelength sweep exhibits almost no noise as it can be seen in Fig. 1 (b) which was acquired with a real-time oscilloscope (Keysight DSOZ634A, 63 GHz, 160 GSa/s) and a 50 GHz photodiode (Finisar XPDV2320R). Due to the 20-22 ns rise- and fall-times of our BOA driver (Wieserlabs WL-LDC10D) and the high modulation speed required for 32x optical buffering, the edges of the sweep are smoothed out. We expect to solve this by using high-speed BOA driver electronics.

Fig. 1 (a) Output spectrum with spectral width of 113 nm (b) Intensity trace of the direct laser output measured with a 50 GHz photodiode and a 63 GHz real-time oscilloscope (c) Corresponding zero sensitivity roll-off over ~ 33 mm (approx. 1.7 GHz/mm imaging depth)

For OCT, a key performance characteristic of light sources is the sensitivity decay over depth (roll-off). To evaluate this property, the roll-off is measured by incrementally introducing path length differences of ~ 5 mm in a Mach-Zehnder type interferometer. At each step interference signals are acquired (using the same detection setup as described above), postprocessed and recalibrated. The resulting point-spread-functions are shown in Fig. 1 (c). The FDML laser is rolling-off with the 3 dB bandwidth of the photodiode's frequency response (50 GHz) corresponding to a path length mismatch of ~ 33 mm. This indicates that the FDML laser has a zero roll-off within our hardware limitations.

The presented 13.4 MHz FDML laser is a decisive step towards next-level MHz-OCT for intra-surgical optical coherence tomography and can enable high resolution live 4D OCT. We will show in-depth performance characteristics of the current laser setup and its stability.

References

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